

Astrology and Women: A Journey Through Time

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Abstract

Women are the custodians of culture and part of society; they are an important component of the development process and a significant part of social structure and Cultural values: They are expected to maintain and sustain social values and norms. Many of the changes that contemporary society has experienced are the result of specific ongoing trends, particularly astrology. The women's journey is the primary focus of the current paper. Women were initially perceived as inferior members of society in these areas of astrology; however, as time progressed, society's acceptance of women also brought about significant changes in their lives. Significant changes in the roles of women have resulted from the feminist revolution's ideological influence. Particularly, the three phases of feminism. Therefore, the current investigation attempts to learn about the progress of women, with a special focus on the perspective of women who practice astrology in their personal lives. A belief that the position of celestial bodies at the time of birth has a profound influence on personality is the theoretical foundation upon which astrology predicts the compatibility of the relationship between two individuals. (Orion, 2007). The astrological perspective suggests that the celestial positions are the outcome of the individual's knowledge and sense of unity. Orian posits that a relationship is characterised by a strong commitment, which may be crucial when the celestial bodies align at the appropriate moment. He also believes that this alignment affects their current existence. However, the practice of astrology to improve one's quality of life is an ancient tradition. There has been a significant increase in the number of female astrologers and astrology searchers in the twenty-first century, as women have become more prevalent in the contemporary commercial world. The number of women who are both professionals and aspirants in these fields has increased significantly particularly in the field of social media. The current analysis incorporates secondary data from the A doctoral progress report.

Keywords: Astrology, social media, women, and performance of gender.

Introduction

Throughout their lifetimes, women experience multiple challenges, such as physical challenges, Reproductive challenges, psychological challenges, career challenges, and so on, which cause them to seek assistance from specific individuals, such as astrologers, to overcome the most challenging periods of their lives. They handle the challenges of their current life problems with confidence and become mentally calm. Here, astrology, an ancient practice, leads them to believe that it may be of assistance during specific periods of hardship. "The study of the movements and relative positions of celestial bodies interpreted as influencing human affairs and the natural world" (Oxford Dictionary of Phrases and Fable, 2024). The present situation of a woman can be realised by understanding the challenging issues of astrology. Here, it is important to note that the definition of fable posits that human activities are cyclically dependent on celestial bodies, which in turn predict the future events

of the individuals. The features that astrology implements into the lives of individuals and couples are illustrated by the topics of relationships and careers, which are typically found in magazines and newspapers (Crowe, 1990). Crowe's concepts represent the dynamic changes that occur in the process of existence today. The inclusion of these elements in newspapers and magazines motivates individuals, particularly women, to make informed decisions. Concerning the concept of astrology, which focuses on women, why are women concerned with the future? Additionally, the question related to specialists arises: Why is there a greater number of female astrologers in the current society? Associations and organisations are playing significant roles in modern society by conducting online webinars regarding astrology diploma courses and also appointments to seek astrologers, illustrating the influence. In addition, the preferences of women or men are being considered. Astrology's public opinion, professional practices, and critiques have been extensively examined by organisations such as the International Society for Astrological Research (ISAR). This type of shift in knowledge sources results in the ongoing appeal of astrology, particularly for women, as a means of personal growth and appropriate guidance. According to a 2018 report by the Pew Research Centre, 29% of Americans under the age of thirty are believers in astrology. Women are particularly engaged with its findings. The outcome data of (PRC) also indicates that women constitute a greater proportion of astrology applicants than males; women are more numerous. Astrology is criticised by Theodore Adorno (2002) as a "pseudo-science" that encourages reliance among individuals seeking coping strategies, despite being criticised by one of the sociologists on astrology. Its continued popularity is underscored by its ability to satisfy emotional and social needs, particularly for women, and its adaptability to societal changes. Adorno claims that astrology lacks the benefit of empirical evidence and does not incorporate scientific methodology. Nevertheless, it can attract, gain trust, and depend on individuals through the use of methods or techniques to manage stress, reduce emotional stress, and seek solutions to problems. This generally accepted view is not supported by scientific evidence. As demonstrated by Adorno.

The Historical Importance of Women in Astrology

Understanding women's long history in astrology, which is based on celestial observation of human life cycles. covers the culture of practices and the rise in attitudes about astrology among women and female astrologers. Astrology provides a framework that integrates personal experiences with more general celestial events, thereby assisting cultures in establishing order and purpose in an unpredictable universe. Astrology, frequently referred to as the "grandmother of modern science," played a critical role in the early development of systematic knowledge. The focus on the real world and the interpretation of numerically explained objects is the source of later disciplines, such as astronomy and mathematics (Bauer & Durant, as referenced in Eamon, 2013). This illustrates the dual nature of astrology—as both an academic and spiritual pursuit. Offering early cultures, a means of interpreting their surroundings, assists in healing the divide between mystical traditions and the emerging scientific method. The continuous pursuit of knowledge by humanity can be seen in astrology, which offers insights that overcome personal beliefs and influence broader traditions.

The Renaissance was a significant milestone in the field of astrology, as it surpassed intellectual and social barriers, thereby influencing both public and elite culture (Campion, 2009). Astrology encouraged intellectual discourse, which as per the directions of the sovereign court influenced the contemporary expression of art. The concentrated social group throughout multiple aspects of society is sociologically related to the uniting of cultural elements. Astrology has evolved into a common language that unites individuals through their shared values and traditions. This clarifies how belief systems such as astrology serve not only as personal guides but also as a means of guiding society as a whole. Horoscopes have entered the cultural traditions of ancient civilisations such as Mesopotamia and India, thereby influencing us beyond Europe.

Since astrology is a cause for concern, it also encompasses a diverse array of problem-solving methods. To guarantee economic growth and societal stability, Mesopotamia integrated astrological techniques with political governance and agricultural cycles (Greenbaum, 2015). Astrology's integration into societal structures, as witnessed in Mesopotamia and India, shows its importance in meeting both practical and spiritual demands. Women have traditionally played important roles in these circumstances, interpreting cosmic patterns and advising within cultural norms. This participation allowed women to shape societal decisions while negotiating patriarchal systems. Astrology's vast and ongoing popularity continues to empower women by offering a framework for self-expression, identity exploration, and connection across cultural boundaries. In India, astrology was closely associated with Vedic traditions, which had a significant impact on the country's culture, social norms, and personal preferences. These illustrations indicate the global reach of astrology and its ability to satisfy both practical and spiritual needs. Its general popularity illustrates the social function of astrology in establishing common systems of meaning across many cultural contexts. Consequently, its worldwide connections are expanding daily.

Throughout history, women have played a significant role in the field of astrology. They were priestesses and diviners in primitive communities. Their perspectives on celestial events frequently served as a guide for leaders in the formulation of critical decisions, ranging from governance to religious ceremonies (Holden, 2006). In a social context, this shows the critical role that women played in maintaining cultural and spiritual institutions, despite their limited involvement in social media groups. Women were able to influence patriarchal systems by presenting themselves as mediators between the celestial and the human. This reveals how astrology provided a debate for female agency and power.

Due to the current society's interest in astrology in their daily lives, women utilise the opportunity to resolve obstacles in their lives. However, the study of astrology is still influenced by the heritage of women in the present day. By advocating for both scholarly and popular interpretations, female astrologers have guaranteed the relevance of astrology in contemporary society (Burton, 2020). The capacity of social media platforms to engage with a broad range of populations and reach global audiences has been significantly impacted by their expansion. Using blogs, social media, and applications, women have transformed astrology into a user-friendly and engaging tool for self-expression and empowerment. This digital revolution underscores the adaptability of astrology and the evolving roles of women as leaders in the intellectual and societal domains.

Women are increasingly showing their freedom in making decisions about their lives in light of this. The resurgence of astrology on digital platforms also signifies a broader cultural shift. Loftus (2019) notes that women are at the cutting edge of the recovery of astrology, utilising it as a means to challenge conventional systems and create communities of shared experiences. By incorporating technology into contemporary cultural structures, women have expanded the field of astrology. This expansion is indicative of the ongoing discourse regarding identity, agency, and power as women heal and redefine their roles within society.

The two functions of astrology, as a scientific indicator and as a societal instrument, are evident in its history. Women's ongoing contributions to the evolution of astrology show their significant role in the preservation and change of astrological techniques, from ancient female priestesses to contemporary social media influencers. This continuity indicates how astrology has grown to suit different social situations while still offering an important framework for comprehending the relationship between the individual and the universe.

Feminine Aspects in Astrology:

The concept of the feminine aspects is closely associated with astrology and includes the creative qualities associated with celestial motions, as well as nature, which provides care. In astrology, the symbolism frequently conveys themes of harmony, change, and connectivity, which are derived from these typical qualities. The connection between femininity and the universe is centred on the potential of astrology to improve emotional sensitivity and self-awareness in women who are compromising challenging social realities. Astrology prioritises the interpretation of heavenly patterns that elucidate human experiences, serving as a long-standing conceptual connection between mysticism and scientific inquiry. Astrology established a methodical knowledge framework that influenced various disciplines, such as mathematics and astronomy, through the application of numerical analysis and the emphasis on universal regularities (Bauer & Durant, as cited in Eamon, 2013). The intellectual validity of the subject has been shown in ancient civilisations through the integration of astrology, spirituality, and reason. Women were typically significant agents in this context, particularly in their roles as spiritual advisers, as they were able to realise celestial patterns and connect them with societal expectations.

Astrology underwent significant transformations during the Renaissance, as it influenced both high and low culture, thereby influencing the thought processes and decision-making processes of individuals throughout Europe (Campion, 2009). Over the past century, astrology has evolved into a universal cultural language that has influenced numerous aspects of life, including government and art. Women contributed to the increased recognition of astrology, despite the fact that they were occasionally prohibited from attending public academic meetings. The fact that they transformed astrological knowledge into practical advice indicates their role as cultural mediators who connected scientific perspectives with everyday issues, particularly those related to family and society.

The course of world events was altered by the integration of astrology into the culture of regions such as ancient India and Mesopotamia, which extends beyond Europe (Greenbaum, 2015). Women who participated in events where they told predictions in Mesopotamia combined astronomy with the planning of their political and agricultural

policies. This maintained the stability of society. The use of astrology by women was significant for Vedic purposes in India, as they informed people about positive events and periods in their lives. This reveals how women in various cultures adapted astrology in keeping with their traditions, thereby highlighting their roles as spiritual and social leaders and maintaining its connections. Heliadora, a Greco-Roman astrologer, is further evidence that women have played a significant role in astrology for an extended period. Her gravestone is dedicated to her intellect. Heliadora's utilisation of astrology to identify the significant but occasionally disregarded accomplishments of women challenges conventional narratives regarding intellectual history that have been regulated by men. Her work is a component of a broader trend in which women assert their knowledge of subjects that are typically considered to be the exclusive domain of males. She employs astrology as a strategy to gain social respect and significance.

In ancient societies, women who served as priestesses and diviners were capable of reading the constellations and assisting leaders in making critical decisions (Holden, 2006). These occupations established women as a critical link between the spiritual and material worlds by allowing them to influence community standards and the government. This shows the specific field in which astrological women may have influence in a society that is primarily male-dominated, where their spiritual knowledge is typically regarded as significant.

Modern times have seen a significant increase in the number of women who are making astrological contributions. Burton (2020) highlighted the importance of female astrologers in bringing together ancient practices with contemporary interpretations through the use of popular media and academic studies to engage a broader audience. Women have transformed astrology into a universally available instrument with the development of online platforms. This has facilitated the establishment of international organisations and altered its application as a tool for personal liberation. Thanks to the internet, astrology has become easier to understand for women from all backgrounds. They can now establish a connection with and serve in the field.

Haar concludes that "The late 20th-century feminist resurgence of astrology positioned it even more as a tool for analysing various tales of identity and power" by examining the history and the flow of the systems in society by women towards astrology (Vonder Haar, 2019). Women have started using astrology not only for personal advice but also to challenge gender roles and achieve independence. Therefore, the integration of astrology with broader feminist movements is a spiritual undertaking and a social framework for communal empowerment and self-discovery. According to Loftus (2019), women are currently spearheading the contemporary revival of astrology, particularly in their capacities as digital educators and individuals with a significant following. Women are once again considering astrology as a means of protesting the typical distribution of power and knowledge. This is the process of establishing organisations in which emotional support and shared experiences are highly valued and where all individuals feel at home. This leadership demonstrates how women are constantly adapting astrology to meet the requirements of society by combining ancient knowledge with contemporary ideas.

The continual significance of astrology as a cultural and intellectual effort is made clear by its relationship with the feminine character. The history of astrology has been significantly influenced by women, from primitive priestesses who served as leaders to contemporary online stars who advocate for the community. This ongoing transformation not

only indicates the adaptability of astrology but also shows the determination and cleverness of women in redefining its significance in historical and cultural contexts.

Women Who Influenced Roman Astrology

Occasionally, the contributions of renowned males in the political hierarchy are highlighted in discussions of ancient astrology, thereby covering the critical roles that women played. However, in Roman society, the astrological influence of women was both indirect and significant, frequently influencing the making of major choices that were made behind what was happening. The Roman emperor Hadrian is a notable example, as his rule and achievements were greatly influenced by the dependence on astrologically trained women. The major responsibilities that these women bore as celestial phenomenon interpreters and advisors are underscored by notable events in Hadrian's life, which subsequently influenced personal and political decisions (Lady Science, 2020). Their contributions illustrate how astrology was utilised by women to gain influence and authority in high-level decision-making, rather than purely as a government instrument. Knowing the responsibilities of these women as astrologers and counsellors enables us to learn the extent to which astrology should be valued in Roman society.

Goffman's Theory of Gender Performance in Astrology

Astrology provides an alternate viewpoint on gender dynamics, particularly how women have navigated their roles in disciplines that are predominantly male as a sociocultural practice. By drawing on Goffman's (1959) theory of gender performance, it is possible to gain a deeper knowledge of the ways in which women astrologers, both historically and in the present day, managed societal expectations to establish areas of influence and power.

1. Gender Roles:

In terms of performance, Goffman believes that individuals "perform" gender roles according to societal expectations, thereby presenting themselves in a manner meant to bring up specific emotions. The qualities traditionally associated with femininity, such as sensitivity and empathy, were reflected in the work of women astrologers in both ancient and modern settings. These presentations kept to social norms, which helped them to deal with limited environments while maintaining their professional authority. Women, for example, utilised their perceived religious knowledge and sensitivity to attract approval and trust in a field that was predominantly male-dominated in Roman astrology. This indicates how gender performance facilitated women's involvement in astrology, thereby indirectly challenging normal power structures.

2. Identity Negotiating:

Goffman points out the dynamic nature of identity by suggesting that individuals discuss their positions in social environments through conscious performances. It was shown by female astrologers, who held to social norms of femininity while showing their expertise. For example, women who advised Roman officials confirmed their roles as astrologers and counsellors by integrating their intellectual abilities with their intuitive "feminine" characteristics. By utilising this dual strategy, they were able to externally conform to the gender norms of their age while simultaneously demonstrating authority and influence.

Historical documents clearly show this dual bargaining, like those of the astrologer Forman, whose clients comprised both underprivileged people and affluent elites. Many of Forman's clients were women who were seeking answers to personal calamities, such as disease or financial issues, within a celestial framework (Eamon, 2013). Astrology provided these women with an explanation that turned irregularity into order, thereby allowing them to evaluate their challenges within broader celestial dynamics. From this standpoint, astrology functioned as both a personal coping mechanism and a social instrument for the construction of meaning, thereby confirming Goffman's argument that social structures have a major effect on performance and identity.

3. Sociology's Tool for Astrology:

From a sociological perspective, the ongoing popularity of astrology shows its role in satisfying the ever-present human desire for control and meaning in the face of confusion. Despite the advancements in science and technology, individuals continue to seek guidance from astrology regarding their personal issues. A significant number of them are of the opinion that the challenges of life are decided by celestial forces. This everlasting curiosity, which is made stronger by certain platforms, underscores the adaptability of astrology in the context of modern culture. These websites democratise astrological techniques, particularly for women, by offering easily available and participatory tools. As a result, they provide a source of emotional support and identity building.

Goffman's paradigm allows the observation of women astrologers as active actors who manage and get around power within patriarchal societies through performance, rather than only as members of a tradition. Their capacity to maintain a balance between societal expectations and their personal and professional authority demonstrates how astrology offers a platform for both cooperation and opposition. In a social context, this dynamic is symbolic of broader trends in gender performance, in which marginalised groups utilise cultural frameworks to exhibit agency in accordance with established standards. The continuing popularity of astrology, particularly among women, may be regarded as a reflection of its societal scope. It offers a unique platform for discussions of identity, thereby merging individual goals for self-expression with the societal pressures to fit in. By contextualising women's roles in astrology within Goffman's theory, we can gain a more profound understanding of the ways in which cultural traditions, such as astrology, function as spaces for social unity, opposition; and empowerment.

Gendered Analysis and Astrological Perspective in Contemporary Society

Multiple societal activities reflect and maintain gender dynamics; astrology provides a forum for women to investigate empowerment, self-expression, and identity-building. Nicholas Champion's (2012) observations on the accuracy of astrology, its popularity on social media, and the general awareness of sun signs, particularly among women, provide a valuable foundation for evaluating its contemporary importance. These topics are directly related to the manner in which women engage with astrology, as both active participants in its digital advancement and as individuals who face societal expectations.

1. Astrology's Confirmed Effectiveness:

Throughout history, women have been excluded from official intellectual discussions, frequently disregarded in scientific discussions, and restricted to the margins of knowledge generation. Although some regard astrology as a pseudoscience, it offers an alternative theory that is a popular choice for women who are interested in exploring their identities beyond the limitations of normal thinking. This additional domain enables individuals to empower themselves by validating subjective experiences and emotional intelligence as forms of knowledge. Sometimes, women prioritise their ethical and personal worth over scientific confirmation when employing astrology as a means of self-discovery and social pressure management. As a result, astrology is regarded as a valuable instrument that is valued for its ability to encourage human awareness and agency, rather than being limited by common accuracy standards.

2. The Expansion of Astrology on Social Media:

The manner in which women conduct and perceive astrology has been significantly altered by the growing number of internet platforms. In interactive areas established by social media platforms such as YouTube, TikTok and Instagram, women have the opportunity to share personal experiences, interact with astrological information, and network with like-minded individuals. Pınarbaşı (2021) underlines how the "virtual world, which goes beyond all kinds of institutional structures and authorities in different contexts, has brought people of all beliefs together on a platform where they can connect." Akgül's 2017 phenomenon, "media faith," underscores the extent to which digital platforms facilitate the democratization of astrology. Women influencers and astrologers have revolutionised the distribution of astrological content by utilising these platforms, transforming it from traditional periodicals to a more interactive and readily available field. In the past, publications such as *She* revolutionised the manner in which astrology was presented and incorporated technology to increase its accessibility (Franklin, 2008). The role of women as consumers and creators of astrological material has been further enhanced by the evolution of social media. These internet communities are actively established by women, who use astrology as both a tool for personal development and a means of connection. They are not merely passive consumers. This transformation illustrates the extent to which technology has empowered women to shape the astrological discourse in a manner that is reflective of their personal experiences and the requirements of the group.

3. Determine Your Sun Sign:

According to Champion (2012), approximately 90% of individuals are aware of their solar sign, underscoring the cultural significance of astrology. From a feminist perspective, this understanding of sun signs underscores how astrology provides women with a framework for analysing their identities. Understanding one's solar sign is the first step in accessing more in-depth astrological research. This process assists women in evaluating their societal expectations, relationships, and responsibilities. This method aids women in dealing with challenging social relationships and the communication of their experiences within a narrative framework. The sun signs are organised into groups that exhibit a variety of behaviours and mannerisms. Fire, earth, air, and water are the four teams that illustrate the characteristics of specific sun signs (Mitchell, 1995, 52). According to Mitchell, the primary

four divisions in astrology are represented by the influence of the sun sign. Given this, the sun signs at birth symbolise the primary identity, personality, and essence of an individual, including qualities such as commitment, resolve, ego, self-confidence, and fortitude.

Additionally, it exemplifies the distinctiveness of the sun sign and aligns with feminist principles of self-awareness and empowerment. It encourages women to think about more general cosmic themes and establish a connection with them, thereby enabling them to reconcile their objectives with the responsibilities of society. As demonstrated by Champion's research, the significance of astrology is further underscored by its prevalence in digital environments, which offer women a convenient and timely method of engaging with self-discovery and the development of a collective identity.

Stability and Sociological Integration

The themes identified by Champion (2012) are a continuation of Goffman's perspectives on gender performance, as they demonstrate how women employ astrology to navigate their identities within societal constraints. This process of compromise is further facilitated by social media and digital tools, which offer spaces for women to perform, express, and change their roles without the restrictions of traditional hierarchies. A powerful sociological instrument, astrology provides a framework for balancing societal expectations with personal aspirations, while Goffman's framework emphasises the performative nature of identity. The dual function of astrology as a socio-cultural phenomenon and a mechanism for empowerment is evident in its contemporary popularity, particularly among women. Its capacity for combining intimate knowledge with collective significance supports its importance in contemporary society, connecting individual requirements with broader sociological dynamics.

Digital Astrology Platforms for Empowerment

It is puzzling that astrology has not only endured but has also achieved unprecedented levels of popularity in the face of scientific and technological advancements (National Science Board, 2020). Astrology has changed to accommodate the new communication technologies and human interaction with them as society becomes more digital. Even though astrology was previously limited to print media and specialised groups, technological advancements have significantly enhanced its influence and elevated it to a significant social and cultural event in contemporary society.

Significant media historical events influenced the availability of astrology. For example, her periodical revolutionised the field in 1970 by introducing specialised computer software, thereby enhancing the marketability and relevance of astrology in popular culture (Franklin, 2008). This revolutionised the distribution of astrology and mirrored the advancements in communication technology that were more general. Women's magazines were the first to publish weekly horoscopes, which introduced astrology into the mainstream media and increased its appeal to younger consumers.

In contemporary society, digital platforms have enhanced astrology to create a personalised, interactive, and readily accessible experience. From career decisions to emotional well-being, applications such as AstroTalk, AstroSage, GaneshaSpeaks, Clickastro, and MyPandit have played a significant role in this transformation by offering a

wide variety of personalised services that cover a variety of aspects of life. These websites facilitate women's engagement with astrology on their terms by offering straightforward and practical tools, thereby building self-discovery and agency.

Additionally, mass media campaigns serve as a powerful illustration of the extent to which astrology influences the lives of the general people. For example, Bharti Singh, an Indian comedian and actress, appeared in a YouTube commercial for AstroTalk, where she shared a personal account of how an astrologer's prediction affected her life. Singh initially recalled that an astrologer suggested her prominence on television when she was young, a notion that seemed silly. Singh reflected on the astrologer's prediction years later, following a request to audition for a comedy program. She drew a connection between the prediction and her journey to becoming a renowned comedian, who was frequently referred to as the "Laughter Queen." Singh's narrative serves as an illustration of the potency with which astrology can connect with individuals and provide them with opportunities and hope that align with their objectives. However, the widespread appeal of astrology has not been without controversy. Adorno (2002) and other scholars argue that mass media diminishes astrology to a technique for attracting readership and increasing sales, as it is primarily employed for commercial gain by astrologists. Adorno suggests that astrology is frequently employed in magazines and newspapers to increase reader trust, thereby influencing editorial policies more by their entertainment value than by their substantive or interpretive impact. In the same way, Bernstein (2011) observes that the institutionalisation and objectification of privacy and personal engagement through commercialised channels sometimes serve to promote commodification over actual knowledge in the context of astrology's public image.

Even in the face of these objections, astrology holds immense personal significance for so many women. They regard astrology as a tool for self-discovery, emotional support, and empowerment, rather than a source of pleasure or profit. Through consultations, horoscopes, and personalised readings, women typically acquire the necessary resources to navigate life's obstacles, including career decisions and romantic relationships. Astrology's adaptability in meeting diverse social requirements is emphasised by its dual nature as a highly personal profession and a marketed product. In terms of social implications, the growth of digital astrological websites indicates a more extensive cultural transformation. These websites provide a platform for women to cultivate personal relationships with others, share stories, and investigate their identities. Digital platforms democratise access to astrology by combining modern technology with traditional astrological methods, thereby empowering and reinforcing the instrument for community formation. Despite the concerns raised by critics such as Adorno regarding the dangers of commercialisation, the continued prevalence of astrology underscores its significance as a cultural phenomenon that connects individual knowledge with communal misconceptions.

The process by which astrology has evolved on digital media is growing rapidly and its ability to adapt to changing times while still maintaining its fundamental function as a tool for the formulation of meaning. The continuous astrological participation of women in contemporary environments is indicative of not only personal objectives but also provides a perspective through which more general societal dynamics—including the commercialisation of cultural practices, identity formation, and community building—can be observed.

Conclusion

Astrology's continuous connection with women is representative of its significant historical and contemporary significance. It has provided women with a framework throughout generations for dealing with their social responsibilities and identities, leading to self-discovery. Astrology provided women residing in patriarchal environments with an additional platform to demonstrate their independence and appreciate their individuality. Despite its great importance, its relevance has evolved to align with modern circumstances. Astrology, which was initially a specialised interest, has transformed into an instrument that is both freely accessible and engaging as a result of the digital revolution. Currently, women engage with it on a variety of platforms, utilising it for personal development and social networking, as well as connecting with global companies. Astrology offers a communal framework that encourages emotional support and communication among those who follow it, in addition to its value. It continues to integrate personal reflection with shared experiences to provide a platform for connection and solidarity. Astrology is a dynamic cultural practice that will be the way to seek help for women who are in search of empowerment, direction, and guidance, despite the criticism it has received. Its significance as a personal and social instrument is underscored by its adaptability in a variety of social contexts. Women continue to engage with the complexities of contemporary life by employing astrology to address issues of identity, community, and self-expression. As a result, their significance in managing these concerns is heightened.

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